

RISK FACTORS AND PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING OF STUDENTS IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN

D.R. Rakhmanova

Non-Governmental Higher Educational Institution Profi University, Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *This article addresses the issue of psychological well-being among university students in Uzbekistan based on expert evaluations and psychodiagnostics. The conducted pilot multi-screening study allowed for the identification of key factors influencing students' psycho-emotional state, including academic status, ethnic, and gender differences. The analysis of the university environment revealed its significant impact on students' satisfaction levels and psychological state. Additionally, the research highlighted the prevalence of self-harming behavior and suicidal risks among students, underscoring the need for the implementation of preventive programs and psychological support. The obtained results may be used to improve the psychological assistance system in universities.*

Keywords: *psychological well-being, students, higher education, psychodiagnostics, risk factors, university environment, self-harming behavior, suicidal risks, psycho-emotional state, prevention.*

Modern educational conditions in universities place high demands on the psycho-emotional state of students, which makes the use of effective methods for diagnosing their psychological well-being relevant. This study analyzes the significance of psychodiagnostic techniques and expert methods in identifying students' needs for psychological support and their role in assessing the factors affecting the availability and effectiveness of psychological services. The application of psychodiagnostic methods [1,2] not only allows for the identification of individual characteristics of students in the context of their susceptibility to psychological stressors, but also determines their readiness to seek specialized psychological help and analyzes the conditions affecting the functioning of psychological services.

Despite the importance of expert methods as a tool for identifying the need for psychological support, they cannot be considered among university lecturers as alternative methods for psychodiagnostic examination of the student body. It should be noted that expert methods, relying on subjective interpretations by specialists, allow for identifying only general trends and the most common maladaptive psycho-emotional states of students, without taking into account the individual differences in the mental state of each student. Therefore, there is a need for a comprehensive approach that combines expert evaluations and empirical psychodiagnostic methods.

In order to address the limitations inherent in expert-only evaluation methods, a pilot multi-screening study was conducted at three leading universities in Uzbekistan: the Uzbek State University of World Languages (UzSUWL), the Tashkent Medical Academy (TMA), and the private university Profi University.

The results of this study provided more differentiated and objective data on the psychological well-being of the student body. As established, a significant portion of students demonstrates high levels of anxiety, signs of emotional burnout, and chronic stress, which indicates the necessity of developing and implementing targeted preventive and corrective programs. Additionally, the analysis of students' attitudes towards psychological help revealed a number of barriers, including insufficient awareness of the functioning psychological services in universities, as well as the persisting stigma around seeking professional psychological support. These results underscore the importance and need for the implementation of comprehensive institutional measures aimed at enhancing psychological literacy among student youth and improving the accessibility of psychological and consultative services.

The study was conducted using a questionnaire method among first- and third-year students, which allowed for accounting the impact of academic status and the specifics of the educational process on their psychological perception. The sampling structure considered the ethnic-cultural composition of the groups, which is an important characteristic of the higher education system in Uzbekistan, where differences in the language of instruction (Uzbek or Russian) may affect the cognitive and affective aspects of the educational experience.

The central focus of the study was the analysis of students' subjective health levels. According to the obtained data, 48.7% of respondents rated their health as "good," and when combined with the categories "very good" and "excellent," this indicates a predominance of positive subjective health perceptions among students. However, statistically significant differences in health assessments were found depending on ethnicity: students from national groups demonstrated a higher self-assessment of health compared to those from European groups. This phenomenon may be explained by differences in cultural health perception models, social support within ethnic communities, or characteristics of the educational environment.

Additionally, gender differences were identified: female students rated their health on average lower than male students. This fact may reflect the influence of social, psychological, and possibly physiological factors that lead to different attitudes toward health between men and women in the educational environment.

Thus, the results of the pilot study highlight the need for the use of comprehensive psychodiagnostic methods for a more detailed analysis of students' psycho-emotional state and their needs for psychological support. Furthermore, the identified cultural, social, and gender differences should be considered when developing and implementing psychological programs in universities, ensuring their higher effectiveness and adaptability to the characteristics of the student body.

The evaluation of the overall well-being of the university environment and its impact on student health is an important task when forming effective strategies for supporting students' psychological and physical well-being. In this study, this aspect was analyzed based on student questionnaires, in which they answered questions concerning the university's conditions. The application of a 6-point scale of agreement allowed for quantitatively measuring subjective perceptions of the educational environment in terms of its influence on students' well-being and health.

The results indicate a predominantly positive assessment of the university environment: the average score for the entire sample was 18.43 (SD = 3.19), indicating a relatively high level of student satisfaction. However, the significant variability of the assessments, reflected in the

standard deviation, speaks to the presence of substantial individual differences in environmental perception.

Differences between universities were statistically significant ($F = 9.841$, $p < 0.001$), confirming the heterogeneity of university conditions in terms of student perceptions. Thus, the students of the Tashkent Medical Academy rated the environment most favorably (19.53, $SD = 2.43$), while the ratings of students from Profi University (18.56, $SD = 2.45$) and the Uzbek State University of World Languages (17.64, $SD = 3.75$) were somewhat lower. These differences may be due to both the specific characteristics of the educational process at these universities and organizational factors affecting student well-being.

Comparisons by ethnicity and gender did not reveal significant differences, indicating that perceptions of the university environment's well-being are influenced more by the characteristics of the educational institution than by ethnic or gender factors. This result underscores the need for targeted organizational efforts at the university level to create comfortable conditions conducive to students' psychological well-being.

An additional task of the study was screening risk factors associated with students' mental health, including alcohol consumption, self-harming behavior, and suicidal risks. Data analysis in this area allowed for a more detailed identification of key threats to students' psychological well-being and the development of appropriate preventive measures.

The study showed that most students in Uzbekistan's universities do not face serious risks related to psychoactive substance (PAS) use, self-harming behavior, and suicidal thoughts. However, certain issues do exist and require the attention of university psychological services.

Substance Use According to the study results, the overall prevalence of psychoactive substance use among students is very low. The survey revealed the following:

- Smoking: 93.6% of students had not smoked in the last three months.
- Alcohol: 94.0% of respondents had not consumed alcohol in the last quarter, and 91.9% had never tried alcohol.
- Drugs: all respondents (100%) reported they had not used drugs.
- Inhalants: 98.0% of students had not used inhalants.
- Sedative drugs: 94.3% had not taken sedative substances.

Notably, none of the respondents reported regular use of any psychoactive substances. This suggests a low prevalence of such risks in this sample of students. However, it should be noted that social desirability bias may influence the accuracy of these responses. It is also recommended that qualitative research be conducted to identify factors influencing students' attitudes toward substance use.

Self-harming Behavior The study of self-harming behavior among students revealed that most of them (84.9%) had not engaged in such actions in the past year. However, analysis of the remaining portion of the sample showed that a certain proportion of students had encountered this phenomenon:

- 12.4% of respondents engaged in self-harming actions 1-2 times per year, which may indicate periodic episodes of emotional stress or crisis states;
- 1.3% of respondents reported self-harming monthly, which suggests persistent maladaptive coping mechanisms;

- 1.0% of students engaged in self-harming behavior once a week or more, which may indicate the presence of significant psychological difficulties requiring immediate specialist attention.

Thus, the combined data suggest that approximately one in seven students (15.1%) potentially requires psychological support. These results emphasize the importance of preventive measures aimed at the timely identification and assistance to students prone to self-harming behavior. Further research is needed to analyze the causes and factors contributing to this phenomenon, as well as the development of psychological support programs for at-risk students.

Suicidal Risks According to the study:

- 21.8% of students are at increased risk for suicidal behavior;
- 3.6% have attempted suicide;
- 1.6% reported a high likelihood of attempting suicide in the future.

Statistical analysis did not find significant correlations between suicidal risk levels and demographic characteristics such as gender and ethnicity. However, statistically significant differences were identified based on the type of educational institution. The highest level (7.01, SD = 4.42) of suicidal risk was recorded among students at private universities, which may indicate the influence of socio-psychological factors on emotional well-being. These results highlight the need for a comprehensive analysis of the socio-psychological determinants in the higher education system, as well as the development and implementation of targeted preventive programs aimed at reducing suicidal risk among student youth.

Thus, based on the results of the study, the following conclusions can be drawn. The level of psychoactive substance use among students in Uzbekistan's universities remains relatively low, but it requires further verification and monitoring. Self-harming behavior observed in 14.7% of respondents indicates the need for the development and implementation of preventive measures. Suicidal risks affect a certain portion of the student population (21.8%), highlighting the relevance of preventive strategies within the university system.

It should be taken into account that the most significant influences on students' psychological state may stem from organizational aspects of the educational process and the socio-psychological climate in universities. Therefore, these factors should be considered when developing psycho-pedagogical support programs aimed at increasing students' psychological resilience and creating a favorable educational environment.

In order to enhance the psychological well-being of students in higher education institutions, a comprehensive implementation of scientifically grounded psychological support strategies is required. An essential direction is the development of an institutionalized system of psychological support, which includes strengthening the activities of university psychological services, improving early detection mechanisms for at-risk individuals, and implementing targeted preventive programs. Special attention should be given to the professional development of specialists working in student counseling services, as well as integrating interdisciplinary approaches to the diagnosis and correction of psychological problems.

The prevention of suicidal behavior and self-harming tendencies among student youth requires the development and implementation of scientifically grounded early intervention strategies. It is necessary to organize systematic monitoring of students' psycho-emotional state, use validated psychodiagnostic methods, conduct regular anonymous screenings, and implement crisis interventions with subsequent individualized follow-up.

Creating a favorable educational environment requires creating conditions that support students' psychological adaptation, including improving the socio-psychological climate in universities, implementing educational modules on emotional intelligence development, stress resistance, and crisis coping skills. An important component is the active involvement of student communities in implementing mutual aid programs and support initiatives aimed at strengthening youth mental health.

Effective prevention of psychoactive substance use among students should be based on the principles of a comprehensive approach, including informational and educational campaigns, specialized stress management training, and the development of psychological and social rehabilitation programs. Equally important is the introduction of interdepartmental cooperation between educational institutions, medical organizations, and social support structures, which will enhance the quality of preventive work and reduce potential risks.

To ensure sustainable results and increase the effectiveness of implemented measures, it is necessary to introduce a system of long-term monitoring of students' psychological well-being indicators, conduct large-scale interdisciplinary research aimed at identifying determinants of students' psycho-emotional states, and assess the effectiveness of implemented preventive strategies. The implementation of these recommendations will not only minimize psychological risks but also form scientifically grounded approaches to creating an adaptive educational environment that fosters the personal and professional potential of students.

This study revealed significant differences in the perception of the university environment by students from different educational institutions. However, no significant differences were found by ethnic and gender characteristics, which indicates the primary role of organizational and educational factors in shaping students' psychological well-being.

The results of the risk factor analysis related to mental health emphasize the need for targeted preventive measures. Despite the low prevalence of psychoactive substance use, the identified levels of self-harming behavior and suicidal risks require close attention and the development of effective psychological support programs.

Thus, students' psychological well-being should be considered within a comprehensive approach that includes diagnosis, preventive measures, and organizational changes in universities. The development and implementation of targeted support programs are key steps in creating a favorable educational environment that fosters resilience and mental health among student youth.

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